

The Discovery of a Second Lunar Calendar on Rongorongo Tablet C (Mamari)

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Fig 1. Tablet C 'Mamari'

Abstract

The author identifies a second lunar calendar on Rongorongo Tablet C, also known as the Mamari Tablet.

Author biography

Peter Berrett (ORCID: 0009-0008-7108-755X) is a Melbourne-based independent researcher with 75+ SOHO sungrazer discoveries including the first comet in Parker Solar Probe imagery.

1. Introduction

Rongorongo remains one of the few undeciphered scripts of the world. Traditional approaches have focused on visual symbolism, narrative interpretation, or speculative linguistics. With the exception of the identification of what is believed to be a lunar calendar on Mamari Tablet C in 1958 by Thomas Barthel¹, progress of decipherment has been sparse.

2. Statement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) Use

While AI was occasionally consulted for historical research, to finesse the presentation of this paper and for publishing assistance, any interpretive outputs were treated as non-binding suggestions. The author's final analysis and conclusions are as demonstrated below and AI was not used in the pattern recognition aspects or conclusions of this paper.

¹ T. S. Barthel, *Grundlagen zur Entzifferung der Osterinselschrift* (Hamburg: Cram, de Gruyter & Co., 1958)

3. Analysis and discussion

Discovery of the second lunar calendar, step by step

The following describes how the discovery of the second lunar calendar was made.

The transcription of the recto of Tablet C by Barthel² is reproduced at Annexure A. The image of the recto was loaded into Microsoft Paint (Paint) and the author proceeded to cut and paste using Paint's copy tool. Paint is a simple program but at least it does not hallucinate like AI.

The first step undertaken was to take all the glyphs after the 3rd glyph on line 9 and move them down a considerable distance to allow for later work. Next, several delimiters and delimiter sequences were noticed and used to construct the chart as seen at Annexure B. This is not new work by the author but largely a reconstruction of Barthel's³ lunar calendar. A correction has been made in light of a scribal correction identified by Horley⁴.

The structure of the lunar calendar is a recurring delimiter glyph sequence followed by a series of mostly moon inspired glyphs, crescent shaped and full moon shaped. At the end of each delimiter sequence is a composite glyph with a line coming out from the preceding glyph and down to a fish, much like a fishing line hauling up a newly caught fish. Up until the full moon (first 4 sequences) the fish is pointing upwards and downwards thereafter. It is observed that the fish pointing upwards aligns with the waxing of the moon and the fish pointing downwards with the waning.

The summation of moon-shaped glyphs across the eight sequences yields a total of 31 ($2+6+4+4+5+3+5+2= 31$) moon shaped glyphs (moon nights). The glyphs following the 3rd delimiter sequence might be 3 moons or 4 but that question will be addressed later. It suffices to say that this is essentially the lunar calendar identified by Barthel⁵.

² T. S. Barthel, 'Mamari Tablet (Text C) Recto Line 6-9', *Wikimedia Commons*, https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Barthel_Ca.png [accessed 4 April 2026]

³ Barthel, *Grundlagen*; see also 'Mamari Tablet (Text C) Recto Line 6-9', *Wikimedia Commons*

⁴ Paul Horley, 'Rongorongo Script: Carving Techniques and Scribal Corrections', *Journal de la Société des Océanistes*, 129 (2009), 254

⁵ Barthel, *Grundlagen*, 42

There remain 6 lines of glyphs, most of which include peculiar ‘poles’ of 3 diamonds, some with nodules attached to either side. These glyphs may represent a numerical or counting system; however, the underlying structure of that system is not yet understood. For the purposes of this paper, the stack of diamonds will be referred to as a staff and the nodules as buds. The number of diamonds in a staff varies but staves are always vertical poles.

Looking through the glyphs and disregarding the ‘numbers’ the author noticed a repeating sequence of glyphs (predominantly the same and repeating) and the staff & bud glyphs appeared to follow these in the same way as the moon crescents followed the delimiter sequences in the previously identified lunar calendar (A). The pattern is similar:

Delimiter sequence – staves/buds - delimiter sequence – staves/buds... etc

Following the pattern of Lunar Calendar A, the author respaced the glyphs as shown in Annexure C (latter half of Mamari Tablet recto). As readers will note, there is again a pattern⁶ consisting of a delimiter glyph sequence followed by some glyphs largely consisting of mixed staves with buds or no buds. This block has been titled ‘Lunar Calendar B’. The delimiter sequence generally has 5 glyphs and ends with a character that looks like a hooded anthropomorphic figure.

The next step was to take all of block B and move it next to Lunar Calendar A (the calendar identified by Barthel⁷). Note that it has been aligned one row down. The eighth delimiter sequence for Lunar Calendar A has now been moved down to create more room for Delimiter sequence 7. The two aligned calendars are now shown at Annexure E.

As can be seen, there appears to be a common sequence of 6,4,4,5,3,5 then 2. This pattern is true for both the sequence of nights in Lunar Calendar A and the sequence of buds in Lunar Calendar B, subject to the following.

In each delimiter sequence the furry staff connected to or next to what appears to be a 4 pronged turtle appears to be the primary delimiter but it disappears after sequence 5 and

⁶ After the author’s own independent identification of the sequence, it was noted that the sequence was highlighted by user Kwamikagami in an online wikimedia image although it was not identified as a lunar calendar and the highlighted counting of buds appears incorrect. See *Rongorongo Tablet C (Mamari)*, recto, lines Ca6–Ca9. Digital trace and contrast adjustments by Wikimedia user Kwamikagami, 'File:Rongorongo C-a Mamari calendar.jpg' https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rongorongo_text_C#/media/File:Rongorongo_C-a_Mamari_calendar.jpg [accessed 17 May 2026]; based on photographic plates from Stéphen-Chauvet, *L’île de Pâques et ses mystères* (Paris: Éditions Tel, 1935)

⁷ Barthel, *Grundlagen*, 42

only the second glyph (the second glyph in the delimiter sequence) appears in sequences 6a, 6b and 6c. This suggests that the first glyph is acting as a chapter whereas the second glyph denotes a subsection of a chapter.

In Lunar Calendar B, sequence 6, there is therefore:

1. A secondary delimiter with **2** staves of 3 diamonds (sequence 6a) then;
2. A secondary delimiter with **2** staves of 3 diamonds (sequence 6b) then;
3. A secondary delimiter with **1** staff of 4 diamonds (sequence 6c)

To reinforce the above, all the buds on glyphs 6a, 6b and 6c add up to 5 which matches the sequence of 5 nights in the Lunar Calendar A cycle (7th sequence).

An argument could be made that the two sequences do not in fact match because one has 5 nights in one sequence and {2,2,1} nights in the other. That is a perfectly reasonable argument to make. In rebuttal the author contends that the 5 nights divided into 3 parcels represents the allocation of time (nights) to a particular task, or as having some feature peculiar to the purpose of Lunar Calendar B but that is not relevant to the purpose of Lunar Calendar A. It is further submitted that the truncated delimiter sequence for the {2,2,1} nights indicates a segmenting of a period of time and that the truncated delimiter sequence communicates a commonality between the 5 nights divided into 3 parcels.

The common sequences of the two calendars are unlikely⁸ to have arisen by chance, particularly given that they occur on the same side of the same tablet and share a comparable structural format. The sequences appear to be aligned with one another, and on this basis the second sequence of delimiters is interpreted as representing a related calendrical structure (henceforth referred to as Lunar Calendar B). The term “lunar” is used provisionally. If, for example, Lunar Calendar B reflects an agricultural cycle, the buds may represent days rather than nights. In any case, it appears to follow the same underlying structural pattern as Lunar Calendar A.

It is noted that the buds appear on either side of the glyphs so this may represent mornings and afternoons but this is conjecture. No ethnographic source confirms this.

⁸ A simple illustrative model may be considered: if segment lengths are assumed to fall within a range of six possible values (due to there being up to six buds at any one time), then the number of ordered sequences of length seven would be 6^7 (279,936). Under such a simplified assumption, the probability of reproducing an identical ordered sequence by chance would be low. This is not intended as a formal statistical analysis, but as an indication of the relative rarity of the observed correspondence.

Lunar Calendar B is based on the same lunar calendar used by the Rapanui, the total buds add up to 29 which is just short of the visible lunar cycle of 29.53 days. In view of this, a Rapanui lunar calendar of 29 days seems more plausible than a calendar of 31 days. The question is what do the extra two days in Lunar Calendar A represent?

What follows is merely conjecture, not proof of anything, but it is theorised that the Rapanui had a 29 day calendar with an extra day added every second month. This would give a 29.5 day cycle which is just short of the actual lunar cycle length. In Lunar Calendar A there are two seated figures back to back next to the turtle in the final sequence of glyphs. It is suggested that the back to back characters may represent 'alternating'. Some support for this theory can be found in the 5th sequence of Lunar Calendar A. In most of the sequences, the third delimiter sequence glyph is some kind of bird facing to the right. However, immediately following the full moon the glyph faces to the left and thereafter reverts back to the right. It suggests that a change of some kind has occurred.

Guy⁹ compared the calendars obtained by Thomson (1889), Englert (1948) and Métraux (1940). One variance in the calendars is that Englert's calendar has 7 nights starting after the 6 night numbered sequence and ending with the full moon glyph in Lunar Calendar A. However, Thomson and Métraux identify an extra night thus giving 8 nights not 7.

Each of the authors identifies 2 nights before the six night numbered sequence but these are the darkened nights when the moon is in earth's shadow. They do not appear in Lunar Calendar B and may serve another purpose.

From the perspective of an observer, it does not make sense to start counting moons until one can see a moon or at least part of a crescent. It is difficult to count something that has not appeared yet. It is no surprise then, that the first six visible moons are numbered 1-6 by the Rapanui and this is agreed in each of the calendars. It also makes adjusting the cycle to match up with the observed moons much simpler if one waits until the moon is dark and then starts the next observing cycle when the first sign of a new crescent is observed.

The above assertion aligns with the structure of the Lunar Calendar B. It starts on day 1 (Kokore Tahī) and according to the number of buds has a 29 day cycle. It is possible that

⁹ Jacques B. M. Guy, 'On the Lunar Calendar of Tablet Mamari', *Journal de la Société des Océanistes*, 91.2 (1990), 135-49 (pp. 140-42).

the glyphs preceding Lunar Calendar A or in the final delimiter sequence of Lunar Calendar A (or both) may contain instructions for adding a night every second month.

A structurally similar sequence

A considerable number of glyphs preceding the Lunar Calendar A block exist and these were examined to look for delimiting sequences.

The result 'The Preceding Glyphs Pattern' can be found at Annexure F.

A short recurring delimiter sequence (predominantly two glyphs) is observed elsewhere on the recto; however, unlike the two lunar calendars, the author sees nothing calendrical in that structure.

It is noted that the sequence of a turtle followed by back to back seated figures (boxed in red) is identical to that found in the glyphs in Lunar Calendar A, sequence 8. Put another way that sequence including the back to back characters is found close before the first 2 moons in Lunar Calendar A and immediately before the final 2 moons in Lunar Calendar A.

4. Transcription testing

The above analysis based on Barthel's¹⁰ transcriptions was relatively straightforward. However, a complication emerged. The author is grateful for feedback from Jan Rich-Frel who suggested it would be prudent to check that the Barthel's transcriptions matched that on the Mamari tablet. A search online quickly established that the published photographs of tablet were low resolution and/or incorporated into pdf files.

However, the European Commission funded INSCRIBE project has laser scanned the Mamari Tablet and made a 3D scan and visualisation tool available¹¹ which facilitates close inspection of the relevant glyphs. The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to the EU and INSCRIBE project members for what is an amazingly useful tool.

¹⁰ Barthel, *Grundlagen*, 42

¹¹ "3D Interactive Web Viewer," *INSCRIBE: Invention of Scripts and Their Beginnings*, ERC INSCRIBE Project, Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, accessed May 13, 2026, https://www.inscribercproject.com/3d_viewer_home.php.

The author has analysed the sequences of glyphs and recounted the buds. Annexure G contains snapshots of each staff/bud glyph and his count of the buds on it. The numbers differ slightly from Barthels¹² but speculation will not change the final result. The question is – is this fatal to the author’s conclusion?

Before answering that question one needs to step back and ask – what is the purpose of a lunar calendar? Lunar Calendar A is unlikely to exist just for the purpose of naming periods of time within the lunar month. The delimiter sequences are largely similar to each other and if one was naming periods of time like the 6 Kokore nights, one would expect them to be a range of different names as represented by different glyphs. However, they are largely the same with some minor variations.

The structure of Lunar Calendar B is similar to that of Lunar Calendar A. It exists on the same tablet on the same side (recto) as Lunar Calendar A and repeating glyphs feature (buds) that repeat in the same way as Lunar Calendar A (i.e delimiter – buds - delimiter-buds etc). The total number of buds adds up to 29 or 30 buds which is approximately the length of a lunar cycle.

The pattern of the number of buds, whilst not precisely the same as the pattern of the moons, is nevertheless very similar. The numbers of buds, as shown in Annexure G, often align with the number of moons at similar points in each respective sequence.

¹² Barthel, *Grundlagen*, 42

That there should be some variation in two lunar calendars should not be surprising. If there are two calendars for two different purposes e.g. fishing, agriculture, then two calendars could easily have different fishing and planting periods. Such is the case in the Maramataka¹³, the Maori lunar calendar. The best times for fishing differ from the best times for planting. However, the agricultural¹⁴ and fishing allocations of time fall within a common lunar cycle. Also, the Maramataka demonstrates that a lunar calendar can organise agricultural daytime activity, which would explain why Calendar B features plant-like bud glyphs rather than moon glyphs while still operating within a lunar cycle. The Rapanui and Māori calendars diverged for centuries, so parallels are suggestive, not determinative.

It is worth noting that Barthel's reconstruction does not exactly match the ethnographic calendars recorded by Thomson, Englert, and Métraux¹⁵. Their accounts differ in the number and placement of nights, yet Barthel's reconstruction is accepted because its structural features correspond plausibly to a lunar month. Calendar B should therefore be assessed by the same structural criteria, rather than by a demand for exact correspondence.

5. Conclusions

The sequences identified in the latter half of the recto of Tablet C have a similar structure as Lunar Calendar A and the pattern of buds in these sequences have a similar structure, albeit not exactly identical, to the pattern of nights in Lunar Calendar A. Therefore it is concluded that it is more probable than not that these sequences form a second lunar calendar. This is a structural argument, not a semantic decipherment.

Lunar Calendar A has sequences involving moons and fish whereas Lunar Calendar B has 'buds' and the first 6 buds are attached to what appear to be plant glyphs which is suggestive of an agricultural purpose. If the two calendars have different purposes then the allocation of time to each need not be exactly the same.

¹³ Te Papa (n.d.). 'Nights in the Maramataka | the Māori lunar month'. Available at: <https://www.tepapa.govt.nz/discover-collections/read-watch-play/maori/matariki-maori-new-year/nights-maramataka-maori-lunar> (Accessed: 12 May 2026).

¹⁴ Paul Horley (2011). "Lunar calendar in rongorongo texts and rock art of Easter Island." *Journal de la Société des Océanistes*, 132.

¹⁵ Jacques B. M. Guy, 'On the Lunar Calendar of Tablet Mamari', *Journal de la Société des Océanistes*, 91.2 (1990), 135-49 (p. 137) https://www.persee.fr/doc/jso_0300-953x_1990_num_91_2_2882.

The total of 29-30 total buds suggests that the Lunar Calendar B was either 29 or 30 nights long, commencing on the first sighting of the new moon. In the case of a 29 day lunar cycle, the addition of a day every 2 lunar cycles would more neatly allow the Rapanui to align their calendar with the actual visual lunar cycle however it is not obvious how that extra half day would be accounted for in Lunar Calendar B. There is a range of possible explanations including that after 29 days the Rapanui just waited until they saw the new moon and then started again from there. Then again, the alternating back to back glyphs suggest that an extra night was added every two lunar cycles.

If the lunar cycle per Lunar Calendar B was 30 days long then that aligns with the 30 nights of Lunar Calendar A. Either interpretation suggests a lunar calendrical foundation.

Finally a sequence of glyphs with a similar structure to the two calendars is identified in the first 5 lines of the recto side of tablet C but no alignment with the lunar calendars is noted.

Notwithstanding the author's best effort to count the number of buds, the academic world would benefit from a professional reexamination of Tablet C to form a considered opinion as to why the stave and bud glyphs differ from that drawn by Barthel and to arrive at a more forensic count of the number of buds.

6. Author Note

Peter Berrett is an independent researcher.

Annexure B - Reordered Tablet C (Recto)

13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1

11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1

13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1	U(11
13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1	((((((
13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1	(100
13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1	U(00
13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1	(((((
13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1	((11
13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1	(((((
13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1	((

1. This is a scribal correction identified by Paul Horley

13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1
 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1

Annexure E - Numbering of the two lunar calendars

Lunar calendar A			
ታላቁ)ጠቅላይ		U(17	2
ታላቁ)			6
ታላቁ)ጠቅላይ		(8700	4
ታላቁ)ጠቅላይ		U(00	4
ታላቁ)ጠቅላይ			5
ታላቁ)ጠቅላይ			3
ታላቁ)ጠቅላይ	ጠ		5
ታላቁ)ጠቅላይ	ጠፎረ		2
Total nights = 31			

Lunar Calendar B			
ጠቅላይ)ጠቅላይ	ጠፎረ		6
ጠቅላይ)ጠቅላይ	ጠፎረ		4
ጠቅላይ)ጠቅላይ	ጠፎረ ጠፎረ ጠፎረ		4
ጠቅላይ)ጠቅላይ	ጠፎረ ጠፎረ ጠፎረ		5
ጠቅላይ)ጠቅላይ	ጠፎረ		3
ጠፎረ	ጠፎረ	1	
ጠፎረ	ጠፎረ	2	
ጠፎረ	ጠፎረ	2	5
ጠቅላይ)ጠቅላይ	ጠፎረ		2
Total buds = 29			

1. This is a scribal correction identified by Paul Horley

**Annexure F - Reordered preceding glyphs
(First 5 lines of Tablet C)**

𐎠𐎡𐎢𐎣𐎤𐎥𐎦𐎧𐎨𐎩𐎪𐎫𐎬𐎭𐎮𐎯𐎰𐎱𐎲𐎳𐎴𐎵𐎶𐎷𐎸𐎹𐎺𐎻𐎼𐎽𐎾𐎿𐏀𐏁𐏂𐏃𐏄𐏅𐏆𐏇𐏈𐏉𐏊𐏋𐏌𐏍𐏎𐏏𐏐𐏑𐏒𐏓𐏔𐏕𐏖𐏗𐏘𐏙𐏚𐏛𐏜𐏝𐏞𐏟𐏠𐏡𐏢𐏣𐏤𐏥𐏦𐏧𐏨𐏩𐏪𐏫𐏬𐏭𐏮𐏯𐏰𐏱𐏲𐏳𐏴𐏵𐏶𐏷𐏸𐏹𐏺𐏻𐏼𐏽𐏾𐏿𐐀𐐁𐐂𐐃𐐄𐐅𐐆𐐇𐐈𐐉𐐊𐐋𐐌𐐍𐐎𐐏𐐐𐐑𐐒𐐓𐐔𐐕𐐖𐐗𐐘𐐙𐐚𐐛𐐜𐐝𐐞𐐟𐐠𐐡𐐢𐐣𐐤𐐥𐐦𐐧𐐨𐐩𐐪𐐫𐐬𐐭𐐮𐐯𐐰𐐱𐐲𐐳𐐴𐐵𐐶𐐷𐐸𐐹𐐺𐐻𐐼𐐽𐐾𐐿𐑀𐑁𐑂𐑃𐑄𐑅𐑆𐑇𐑈𐑉𐑊𐑋𐑌𐑍𐑎𐑏𐑐𐑑𐑒𐑓𐑔𐑕𐑖𐑗𐑘𐑙𐑚𐑛𐑜𐑝𐑞𐑟𐑠𐑡𐑢𐑣𐑤𐑥𐑦𐑧𐑨𐑩𐑪𐑫𐑬𐑭𐑮𐑯𐑰𐑱𐑲𐑳𐑴𐑵𐑶𐑷𐑸𐑹𐑺𐑻𐑼𐑽𐑾𐑿𐒀𐒁𐒂𐒃𐒄𐒅𐒆𐒇𐒈𐒉𐒊𐒋𐒌𐒍𐒎𐒏𐒐𐒑𐒒𐒓𐒔𐒕𐒖𐒗𐒘𐒙𐒚𐒛𐒜𐒝𐒞𐒟𐒠𐒡𐒢𐒣𐒤𐒥𐒦𐒧𐒨𐒩𐒪𐒫𐒬𐒭𐒮𐒯𐒰𐒱𐒲𐒳𐒴𐒵𐒶𐒷𐒸𐒹𐒺𐒻𐒼𐒽𐒾𐒿𐓀𐓁𐓂𐓃𐓄𐓅𐓆𐓇𐓈𐓉𐓊𐓋𐓌𐓍𐓎𐓏𐓐𐓑𐓒𐓓𐓔𐓕𐓖𐓗𐓘𐓙𐓚𐓛𐓜𐓝𐓞𐓟𐓠𐓡𐓢𐓣𐓤𐓥𐓦𐓧𐓨𐓩𐓪𐓫𐓬𐓭𐓮𐓯𐓰𐓱𐓲𐓳𐓴𐓵𐓶𐓷𐓸𐓹𐓺𐓻𐓼𐓽𐓾𐓿𐔀𐔁𐔂𐔃𐔄𐔅𐔆𐔇𐔈𐔉𐔊𐔋𐔌𐔍𐔎𐔏𐔐𐔑𐔒𐔓𐔔𐔕𐔖𐔗𐔘𐔙𐔚𐔛𐔜𐔝𐔞𐔟𐔠𐔡𐔢𐔣𐔤𐔥𐔦𐔧𐔨𐔩𐔪𐔫𐔬𐔭𐔮𐔯𐔰𐔱𐔲𐔳𐔴𐔵𐔶𐔷𐔸𐔹𐔺𐔻𐔼𐔽𐔾𐔿𐕀𐕁𐕂𐕃𐕄𐕅𐕆𐕇𐕈𐕉𐕊𐕋𐕌𐕍𐕎𐕏𐕐𐕑𐕒𐕓𐕔𐕕𐕖𐕗𐕘𐕙𐕚𐕛𐕜𐕝𐕞𐕟𐕠𐕡𐕢𐕣𐕤𐕥𐕦𐕧𐕨𐕩𐕪𐕫𐕬𐕭𐕮𐕯𐕰𐕱𐕲𐕳𐕴𐕵𐕶𐕷𐕸𐕹𐕺𐕻𐕼𐕽𐕾𐕿𐖀𐖁𐖂𐖃𐖄𐖅𐖆𐖇𐖈𐖉𐖊𐖋𐖌𐖍𐖎𐖏𐖐𐖑𐖒𐖓𐖔𐖕𐖖𐖗𐖘𐖙𐖚𐖛𐖜𐖝𐖞𐖟𐖠𐖡𐖢𐖣𐖤𐖥𐖦𐖧𐖨𐖩𐖪𐖫𐖬𐖭𐖮𐖯𐖰𐖱𐖲𐖳𐖴𐖵𐖶𐖷𐖸𐖹𐖺𐖻𐖼𐖽𐖾𐖿𐗀𐗁𐗂𐗃𐗄𐗅𐗆𐗇𐗈𐗉𐗊𐗋𐗌𐗍𐗎𐗏𐗐𐗑𐗒𐗓𐗔𐗕𐗖𐗗𐗘𐗙𐗚𐗛𐗜𐗝𐗞𐗟𐗠𐗡𐗢𐗣𐗤𐗥𐗦𐗧𐗨𐗩𐗪𐗫𐗬𐗭𐗮𐗯𐗰𐗱𐗲𐗳𐗴𐗵𐗶𐗷𐗸𐗹𐗺𐗻𐗼𐗽𐗾𐗿𐘀𐘁𐘂𐘃𐘄𐘅𐘆𐘇𐘈𐘉𐘊𐘋𐘌𐘍𐘎𐘏𐘐𐘑𐘒𐘓𐘔𐘕𐘖𐘗𐘘𐘙𐘚𐘛𐘜𐘝𐘞𐘟𐘠𐘡𐘢𐘣𐘤𐘥𐘦𐘧𐘨𐘩𐘪𐘫𐘬𐘭𐘮𐘯𐘰𐘱𐘲𐘳𐘴𐘵𐘶𐘷𐘸𐘹𐘺𐘻𐘼𐘽𐘾𐘿𐙀𐙁𐙂𐙃𐙄𐙅𐙆𐙇𐙈𐙉𐙊𐙋𐙌𐙍𐙎𐙏𐙐𐙑𐙒𐙓𐙔𐙕𐙖𐙗𐙘𐙙𐙚𐙛𐙜𐙝𐙞𐙟𐙠𐙡𐙢𐙣𐙤𐙥𐙦𐙧𐙨𐙩𐙪𐙫𐙬𐙭𐙮𐙯𐙰𐙱𐙲𐙳𐙴𐙵𐙶𐙷𐙸𐙹𐙺𐙻𐙼𐙽𐙾𐙿𐚀𐚁𐚂𐚃𐚄𐚅𐚆𐚇𐚈𐚉𐚊𐚋𐚌𐚍𐚎𐚏𐚐𐚑𐚒𐚓𐚔𐚕𐚖𐚗𐚘𐚙𐚚𐚛𐚜𐚝𐚞𐚟𐚠𐚡𐚢𐚣𐚤𐚥𐚦𐚧𐚨𐚩𐚪𐚫𐚬𐚭𐚮𐚯𐚰𐚱𐚲𐚳𐚴𐚵𐚶𐚷𐚸𐚹𐚺𐚻𐚼𐚽𐚾𐚿𐛀𐛁𐛂𐛃𐛄𐛅𐛆𐛇𐛈𐛉𐛊𐛋𐛌𐛍𐛎𐛏𐛐𐛑𐛒𐛓𐛔𐛕𐛖𐛗𐛘𐛙𐛚𐛛𐛜𐛝𐛞𐛟𐛠𐛡𐛢𐛣𐛤𐛥𐛦𐛧𐛨𐛩𐛪𐛫𐛬𐛭𐛮𐛯𐛰𐛱𐛲𐛳𐛴𐛵𐛶𐛷𐛸𐛹𐛺𐛻𐛼𐛽𐛾𐛿𐜀𐜁𐜂𐜃𐜄𐜅𐜆𐜇𐜈𐜉𐜊𐜋𐜌𐜍𐜎𐜏𐜐𐜑𐜒𐜓𐜔𐜕𐜖𐜗𐜘𐜙𐜚𐜛𐜜𐜝𐜞𐜟𐜠𐜡𐜢𐜣𐜤𐜥𐜦𐜧𐜨𐜩𐜪𐜫𐜬𐜭𐜮𐜯𐜰𐜱𐜲𐜳𐜴𐜵𐜶𐜷𐜸𐜹𐜺𐜻𐜼𐜽𐜾𐜿𐝀𐝁𐝂𐝃𐝄𐝅𐝆𐝇𐝈𐝉𐝊𐝋𐝌𐝍𐝎𐝏𐝐𐝑𐝒𐝓𐝔𐝕𐝖𐝗𐝘𐝙𐝚𐝛𐝜𐝝𐝞𐝟𐝠𐝡𐝢𐝣𐝤𐝥𐝦𐝧𐝨𐝩𐝪𐝫𐝬𐝭𐝮𐝯𐝰𐝱𐝲𐝳𐝴𐝵𐝶𐝷𐝸𐝹𐝺𐝻𐝼𐝽𐝾𐝿𐞀𐞁𐞂𐞃𐞄𐞅𐞆𐞇𐞈𐞉𐞊𐞋𐞌𐞍𐞎𐞏𐞐𐞑𐞒𐞓𐞔𐞕𐞖𐞗𐞘𐞙𐞚𐞛𐞜𐞝𐞞𐞟𐞠𐞡𐞢𐞣𐞤𐞥𐞦𐞧𐞨𐞩𐞪𐞫𐞬𐞭𐞮𐞯𐞰𐞱𐞲𐞳𐞴𐞵𐞶𐞷𐞸𐞹𐞺𐞻𐞼𐞽𐞾𐞿𐟀𐟁𐟂𐟃𐟄𐟅𐟆𐟇𐟈𐟉𐟊𐟋𐟌𐟍𐟎𐟏𐟐𐟑𐟒𐟓𐟔𐟕𐟖𐟗𐟘𐟙𐟚𐟛𐟜𐟝𐟞𐟟𐟠𐟡𐟢𐟣𐟤𐟥𐟦𐟧𐟨𐟩𐟪𐟫𐟬𐟭𐟮𐟯𐟰𐟱𐟲𐟳𐟴𐟵𐟶𐟷𐟸𐟹𐟺𐟻𐟼𐟽𐟾𐟿𐠀𐠁𐠂𐠃𐠄𐠅𐠆𐠇𐠈𐠉𐠊𐠋𐠌𐠍𐠎𐠏𐠐𐠑𐠒𐠓𐠔𐠕𐠖𐠗𐠘𐠙𐠚𐠛𐠜𐠝𐠞𐠟𐠠𐠡𐠢𐠣𐠤𐠥𐠦𐠧𐠨𐠩𐠪𐠫𐠬𐠭𐠮𐠯𐠰𐠱𐠲𐠳𐠴𐠵𐠶𐠷𐠸𐠹𐠺𐠻𐠼𐠽𐠾𐠿𐡀𐡁𐡂𐡃𐡄𐡅𐡆𐡇𐡈𐡉𐡊𐡋𐡌𐡍𐡎𐡏𐡐𐡑𐡒𐡓𐡔𐡕𐡖𐡗𐡘𐡙𐡚𐡛𐡜𐡝𐡞𐡟𐡠𐡡𐡢𐡣𐡤𐡥𐡦𐡧𐡨𐡩𐡪𐡫𐡬𐡭𐡮𐡯𐡰𐡱𐡲𐡳𐡴𐡵𐡶𐡷𐡸𐡹𐡺𐡻𐡼𐡽𐡾𐡿𐢀𐢁𐢂𐢃𐢄𐢅𐢆𐢇𐢈𐢉𐢊𐢋𐢌𐢍𐢎𐢏𐢐𐢑𐢒𐢓𐢔𐢕𐢖𐢗𐢘𐢙𐢚𐢛𐢜𐢝𐢞𐢟𐢠𐢡𐢢𐢣𐢤𐢥𐢦𐢧𐢨𐢩𐢪𐢫𐢬𐢭𐢮𐢯𐢰𐢱𐢲𐢳𐢴𐢵𐢶𐢷𐢸𐢹𐢺𐢻𐢼𐢽𐢾𐢿𐣀𐣁𐣂𐣃𐣄𐣅𐣆𐣇𐣈𐣉𐣊𐣋𐣌𐣍𐣎𐣏𐣐𐣑𐣒𐣓𐣔𐣕𐣖𐣗𐣘𐣙𐣚𐣛𐣜𐣝𐣞𐣟𐣠𐣡𐣢𐣣𐣤𐣥𐣦𐣧𐣨𐣩𐣪𐣫𐣬𐣭𐣮𐣯𐣰𐣱𐣲𐣳𐣴𐣵𐣶𐣷𐣸𐣹𐣺𐣻𐣼𐣽𐣾𐣿𐤀𐤁𐤂𐤃𐤄𐤅𐤆𐤇𐤈𐤉𐤊𐤋𐤌𐤍𐤎𐤏𐤐𐤑𐤒𐤓𐤔𐤕𐤖𐤗𐤘𐤙𐤚𐤛𐤜𐤝𐤞𐤟𐤠𐤡𐤢𐤣𐤤𐤥𐤦𐤧𐤨𐤩𐤪𐤫𐤬𐤭𐤮𐤯𐤰𐤱𐤲𐤳𐤴𐤵𐤶𐤷𐤸𐤹𐤺𐤻𐤼𐤽𐤾𐤿𐥀𐥁𐥂𐥃𐥄𐥅𐥆𐥇𐥈𐥉𐥊𐥋𐥌𐥍𐥎𐥏𐥐𐥑𐥒𐥓𐥔𐥕𐥖𐥗𐥘𐥙𐥚𐥛𐥜𐥝𐥞𐥟𐥠𐥡𐥢𐥣𐥤𐥥𐥦𐥧𐥨𐥩𐥪𐥫𐥬𐥭𐥮𐥯𐥰𐥱𐥲𐥳𐥴𐥵𐥶𐥷𐥸𐥹𐥺𐥻𐥼𐥽𐥾𐥿𐦀𐦁𐦂𐦃𐦄𐦅𐦆𐦇𐦈𐦉𐦊𐦋𐦌𐦍𐦎𐦏𐦐𐦑𐦒𐦓𐦔𐦕𐦖𐦗𐦘𐦙𐦚𐦛𐦜𐦝𐦞𐦟𐦠𐦡𐦢𐦣𐦤𐦥𐦦𐦧𐦨𐦩𐦪𐦫𐦬𐦭𐦮𐦯𐦰𐦱𐦲𐦳𐦴𐦵𐦶𐦷𐦸𐦹𐦺𐦻𐦼𐦽𐦾𐦿𐧀𐧁𐧂𐧃𐧄𐧅𐧆𐧇𐧈𐧉𐧊𐧋𐧌𐧍𐧎𐧏𐧐𐧑𐧒𐧓𐧔𐧕𐧖𐧗𐧘𐧙𐧚𐧛𐧜𐧝𐧞𐧟𐧠𐧡𐧢𐧣𐧤𐧥𐧦𐧧𐧨𐧩𐧪𐧫𐧬𐧭𐧮𐧯𐧰𐧱𐧲𐧳𐧴𐧵𐧶𐧷𐧸𐧹𐧺𐧻𐧼𐧽𐧾𐧿𐨀𐨁𐨂𐨃𐨄𐨅𐨆𐨇𐨈𐨉𐨊𐨋𐨌𐨍𐨎𐨏𐨐𐨑𐨒𐨓𐨔𐨕𐨖𐨗𐨘𐨙𐨚𐨛𐨜𐨝𐨞𐨟𐨠𐨡𐨢𐨣𐨤𐨥𐨦𐨧𐨨𐨩𐨪𐨫𐨬𐨭𐨮𐨯𐨰𐨱𐨲𐨳𐨴𐨵𐨶𐨷𐨹𐨺𐨸𐨻𐨼𐨽𐨾𐨿𐩀𐩁𐩂𐩃𐩄𐩅𐩆𐩇𐩈𐩉𐩊𐩋𐩌𐩍𐩎𐩏𐩐𐩑𐩒𐩓𐩔𐩕𐩖𐩗𐩘𐩙𐩚𐩛𐩜𐩝𐩞𐩟𐩠𐩡𐩢𐩣𐩤𐩥𐩦𐩧𐩨𐩩𐩪𐩫𐩬𐩭𐩮𐩯𐩰𐩱𐩲𐩳𐩴𐩵𐩶𐩷𐩸𐩹𐩺𐩻𐩼𐩽𐩾𐩿𐪀𐪁𐪂𐪃𐪄𐪅𐪆𐪇𐪈𐪉𐪊𐪋𐪌𐪍𐪎𐪏𐪐𐪑𐪒𐪓𐪔𐪕𐪖𐪗𐪘𐪙𐪚𐪛𐪜𐪝𐪞𐪟𐪠𐪡𐪢𐪣𐪤𐪥𐪦𐪧𐪨𐪩𐪪𐪫𐪬𐪭𐪮𐪯𐪰𐪱𐪲𐪳𐪴𐪵𐪶𐪷𐪸𐪹𐪺𐪻𐪼𐪽𐪾𐪿𐫀𐫁𐫂𐫃𐫄𐫅𐫆𐫇𐫈𐫉𐫊𐫋𐫌𐫍𐫎𐫏𐫐𐫑𐫒𐫓𐫔𐫕𐫖𐫗𐫘𐫙𐫚𐫛𐫜𐫝𐫞𐫟𐫠𐫡𐫢𐫣𐫤𐫦𐫥𐫧𐫨𐫩𐫪𐫫𐫬𐫭𐫮𐫯𐫰𐫱𐫲𐫳𐫴𐫵𐫶𐫷𐫸𐫹𐫺𐫻𐫼𐫽𐫾𐫿𐬀𐬁𐬂𐬃𐬄𐬅𐬆𐬇𐬈𐬉𐬊𐬋𐬌𐬍𐬎𐬏𐬐𐬑𐬒𐬓𐬔𐬕𐬖𐬗𐬘𐬙𐬚𐬛𐬜𐬝𐬞𐬟𐬠𐬡𐬢𐬣𐬤𐬥𐬦𐬧𐬨𐬩𐬪𐬫𐬬𐬭𐬮𐬯𐬰𐬱𐬲𐬳𐬴𐬵𐬶𐬷𐬸𐬹𐬺𐬻𐬼𐬽𐬾𐬿𐭀𐭁𐭂𐭃𐭄𐭅𐭆𐭇𐭈𐭉𐭊𐭋𐭌𐭍𐭎𐭏𐭐𐭑𐭒𐭓𐭔𐭕𐭖𐭗𐭘𐭙𐭚𐭛𐭜𐭝𐭞𐭟𐭠𐭡𐭢𐭣𐭤𐭥𐭦𐭧𐭨𐭩𐭪𐭫𐭬𐭭𐭮𐭯𐭰𐭱𐭲𐭳𐭴𐭵𐭶𐭷𐭸𐭹𐭺𐭻𐭼𐭽𐭾𐭿𐮀𐮁𐮂𐮃𐮄𐮅𐮆𐮇𐮈𐮉𐮊𐮋𐮌𐮍𐮎𐮏𐮐𐮑𐮒𐮓𐮔𐮕𐮖𐮗𐮘𐮙𐮚𐮛𐮜𐮝𐮞𐮟𐮠𐮡𐮢𐮣𐮤𐮥𐮦𐮧𐮨𐮩𐮪𐮫𐮬𐮭𐮮𐮯𐮰𐮱𐮲𐮳𐮴𐮵𐮶𐮷𐮸𐮹𐮺𐮻𐮼𐮽𐮾𐮿𐯀𐯁𐯂𐯃𐯄𐯅𐯆𐯇𐯈𐯉𐯊𐯋𐯌𐯍𐯎𐯏𐯐𐯑𐯒𐯓𐯔𐯕𐯖𐯗𐯘𐯙𐯚𐯛𐯜𐯝𐯞𐯟𐯠𐯡𐯢𐯣𐯤𐯥𐯦𐯧𐯨𐯩𐯪𐯫𐯬𐯭𐯮𐯯𐯰𐯱𐯲𐯳𐯴𐯵𐯶𐯷𐯸𐯹𐯺𐯻𐯼𐯽𐯾𐯿𐰀𐰁𐰂𐰃𐰄𐰅𐰆𐰇𐰈𐰉𐰊𐰋𐰌𐰍𐰎𐰏𐰐𐰑𐰒𐰓𐰔𐰕𐰖𐰗𐰘𐰙𐰚𐰛𐰜𐰝𐰞𐰟𐰠𐰡𐰢𐰣𐰤𐰥𐰦𐰧𐰨𐰩𐰪𐰫𐰬𐰭𐰮𐰯𐰰𐰱𐰲𐰳𐰴𐰵𐰶𐰷𐰸𐰹𐰺𐰻𐰼𐰽𐰾𐰿𐱀𐱁𐱂𐱃𐱄𐱅𐱆𐱇𐱈𐱉𐱊𐱋𐱌𐱍𐱎𐱏𐱐𐱑𐱒𐱓𐱔𐱕𐱖𐱗𐱘𐱙𐱚𐱛𐱜𐱝𐱞𐱟𐱠𐱡𐱢𐱣𐱤𐱥𐱦𐱧𐱨𐱩𐱪𐱫𐱬𐱭𐱮𐱯𐱰𐱱𐱲𐱳𐱴𐱵𐱶𐱷𐱸𐱹𐱺𐱻𐱼𐱽𐱾𐱿𐲀𐲁𐲂𐲃𐲄𐲅𐲆𐲇𐲈𐲉𐲊𐲋𐲌𐲍𐲎𐲏𐲐𐲑𐲒𐲓𐲔𐲕𐲖𐲗𐲘𐲙𐲚𐲛𐲜𐲝𐲞𐲟𐲠𐲡𐲢𐲣𐲤𐲥𐲦𐲧𐲨𐲩𐲪𐲫𐲬𐲭𐲮𐲯𐲰𐲱𐲲𐲳𐲴𐲵𐲶𐲷𐲸𐲹𐲺𐲻𐲼𐲽𐲾𐲿𐳀𐳁𐳂𐳃𐳄𐳅𐳆𐳇𐳈𐳉𐳊𐳋𐳌𐳍𐳎𐳏𐳐𐳑𐳒𐳓𐳔𐳕𐳖𐳗𐳘𐳙𐳚𐳛𐳜𐳝𐳞𐳟𐳠𐳡𐳢𐳣𐳤𐳥𐳦𐳧𐳨𐳩𐳪𐳫𐳬𐳭𐳮𐳯𐳰𐳱𐳲𐳳𐳴𐳵𐳶𐳷𐳸𐳹𐳺𐳻𐳼𐳽𐳾𐳿𐴀𐴁𐴂𐴃𐴄𐴅𐴆𐴇𐴈𐴉𐴊𐴋𐴌𐴍𐴎𐴏𐴐𐴑𐴒𐴓𐴔𐴕𐴖𐴗𐴘𐴙𐴚𐴛𐴜𐴝𐴞𐴟𐴠𐴡𐴢𐴣𐴤𐴥𐴦𐴧𐴨𐴩𐴪𐴫𐴬𐴭𐴮𐴯𐴰𐴱𐴲𐴳𐴴𐴵𐴶𐴷𐴸𐴹𐴺𐴻𐴼𐴽𐴾𐴿𐵀𐵁𐵂𐵃𐵄𐵅𐵆𐵇𐵈𐵉𐵊𐵋𐵌𐵍𐵎𐵏𐵐𐵑𐵒𐵓𐵔𐵕𐵖𐵗𐵘𐵙𐵚𐵛𐵜𐵝𐵞𐵟𐵠𐵡𐵢𐵣𐵤𐵥𐵦𐵧𐵨𐵩𐵪𐵫𐵬𐵭𐵮𐵯𐵰𐵱𐵲𐵳𐵴𐵵𐵶𐵷𐵸𐵹𐵺𐵻𐵼𐵽𐵾𐵿𐶀𐶁𐶂𐶃𐶄𐶅𐶆𐶇𐶈𐶉𐶊𐶋𐶌𐶍𐶎𐶏𐶐𐶑𐶒𐶓𐶔𐶕𐶖𐶗𐶘𐶙𐶚𐶛𐶜𐶝𐶞𐶟𐶠𐶡𐶢𐶣𐶤𐶥𐶦𐶧𐶨𐶩𐶪𐶫𐶬𐶭𐶮𐶯𐶰𐶱𐶲𐶳𐶴𐶵𐶶𐶷𐶸𐶹𐶺𐶻𐶼𐶽𐶾𐶿𐷀𐷁𐷂𐷃𐷄𐷅𐷆𐷇𐷈𐷉𐷊𐷋𐷌𐷍𐷎𐷏𐷐𐷑𐷒𐷓𐷔𐷕𐷖𐷗𐷘𐷙𐷚𐷛𐷜𐷝𐷞𐷟𐷠𐷡𐷢𐷣𐷤𐷥𐷦𐷧𐷨𐷩𐷪𐷫𐷬𐷭𐷮𐷯𐷰𐷱𐷲𐷳𐷴𐷵𐷶𐷷𐷸𐷹𐷺𐷻𐷼𐷽𐷾𐷿𐸀𐸁𐸂𐸃𐸄𐸅𐸆𐸇𐸈𐸉𐸊𐸋𐸌𐸍𐸎𐸏𐸐𐸑𐸒𐸓𐸔𐸕𐸖𐸗𐸘𐸙𐸚𐸛𐸜𐸝𐸞𐸟𐸠𐸡𐸢𐸣𐸤𐸥𐸦𐸧𐸨𐸩𐸪𐸫𐸬𐸭𐸮𐸯𐸰𐸱𐸲𐸳𐸴𐸵𐸶𐸷𐸸𐸹𐸺𐸻𐸼𐸽𐸾𐸿𐹀𐹁𐹂𐹃𐹄𐹅𐹆𐹇𐹈𐹉𐹊𐹋𐹌𐹍𐹎𐹏𐹐𐹑𐹒𐹓𐹔𐹕𐹖𐹗𐹘𐹙𐹚𐹛𐹜𐹝𐹞𐹟𐹠𐹡𐹢𐹣𐹤𐹥𐹦𐹧𐹨𐹩𐹪𐹫𐹬𐹭𐹮𐹯𐹰𐹱𐹲𐹳𐹴𐹵𐹶𐹷𐹸𐹹𐹺𐹻𐹼𐹽𐹾𐹿𐺀𐺁𐺂𐺃𐺄𐺅𐺆𐺇𐺈𐺉𐺊𐺋𐺌𐺍𐺎𐺏𐺐𐺑𐺒𐺓𐺔𐺕𐺖𐺗𐺘𐺙𐺚𐺛𐺜𐺝𐺞𐺟𐺠𐺡𐺢𐺣𐺤𐺥𐺦𐺧𐺨𐺩𐺪𐺫𐺬𐺭𐺮𐺯𐺰𐺱𐺲𐺳𐺴𐺵𐺶𐺷𐺸𐺹𐺺𐺻𐺼𐺽𐺾𐺿𐻀𐻁𐻂𐻃𐻄𐻅𐻆𐻇𐻈𐻉𐻊𐻋𐻌𐻍𐻎𐻏𐻐𐻑𐻒𐻓𐻔𐻕𐻖𐻗𐻘𐻙𐻚𐻛𐻜𐻝𐻞𐻟𐻠𐻡𐻢𐻣𐻤𐻥𐻦𐻧𐻨𐻩𐻪𐻫𐻬𐻭𐻮𐻯𐻰𐻱𐻲𐻳𐻴𐻵𐻶𐻷𐻸𐻹𐻺𐻻𐻼𐻽𐻾𐻿𐼀𐼁𐼂𐼃𐼄𐼅𐼆𐼇𐼈𐼉𐼊𐼋𐼌𐼍𐼎𐼏𐼐𐼑𐼒𐼓𐼔𐼕𐼖𐼗𐼘𐼙𐼚𐼛𐼜𐼝𐼞𐼟𐼠𐼡𐼢𐼣𐼤𐼥𐼦𐼧𐼨𐼩𐼪𐼫𐼬𐼭𐼮𐼯𐼰𐼱𐼲𐼳𐼴𐼵𐼶𐼷𐼸𐼹𐼺𐼻𐼼𐼽𐼾𐼿𐽀𐽁𐽂𐽃𐽄𐽅𐽆𐽇𐽋𐽍𐽎𐽏𐽐𐽈𐽉𐽊𐽌𐽑𐽒𐽓𐽔𐽕𐽖𐽗𐽘𐽙𐽚𐽛𐽜𐽝𐽞𐽟𐽠𐽡𐽢𐽣𐽤𐽥𐽦𐽧𐽨𐽩𐽪𐽫𐽬𐽭𐽮𐽯𐽰𐽱𐽲𐽳𐽴𐽵𐽶𐽷𐽸𐽹𐽺𐽻𐽼𐽽𐽾𐽿𐾀𐾁𐾃𐾅𐾂𐾄𐾆𐾇𐾈𐾉𐾊𐾋𐾌𐾍𐾎𐾏𐾐𐾑𐾒𐾓𐾔𐾕𐾖𐾗𐾘𐾙𐾚𐾛𐾜𐾝𐾞𐾟

Annexure G - Transcription comparison with tablet glyphs

Barthel's Transcriptions		Per laser photos		Lunar Calendar A
				2
6			6	6
4			4	4
4			4 possibly 5	4
5			4	5
3			3	3
1			1	
2			2	
2			3	6
2			2	5
				2
Total = 29		Total = 29 or 30		Total = 30

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